

Annotation guide

Syntactic annotation

Tag	Description	Example
Lexical Type		
lex_lexical	Word is spread onto two lines because of the enjambment	a red wheel barrow
Cross-clause Type		
cc_cross_clause	Enjambment occurs between a noun and the relative modifying that noun	Life is a broken-winged bird that cannot fly
Phrase-bounded Types		
pb_verb_chain	Enjambment occurs between a verb and its auxiliary or modal	the lovers who had hurt and forgotten you
pb_verb_cprep	Enjambment occurs between a verb and its lexically-related preposition introducing a prepositional phrase	still, I thought somehow you'd like to know?
pb_verb_adv	Enjambment occurs between a verb and the adverb modifying that verb	Its loveliness increases; it will never Pass into nothingness
pb_noun_adj	Enjambment occurs between and the adjective modifying that noun	beside the white chickens
pb_noun_prep	Enjambment occurs between and the prepositional phrase modifying that noun	I saw a girl with one leg over the rail of a balcony
pb_noun_noun	Enjambment occurs between the two nouns of a compound noun	Alone in my purity World without end
pb_det_noun	Enjambment occurs between a noun and the determiner related to that noun	through the trees

Tag	Description	Example
pb_adj_adv	Enjambment occurs between an adjective and the adverb modifying that adjective	Is it still possible to die for someone else
pb_adj_prep	Enjambment occurs between an adjective and a prepositional phrase modifying that adjective	is it still possible to die for someone else
pb_adj_adj	Enjambment occurs between two adjectives modifying the same noun	I was at that ripe old age of 45
pb_adv_adv	Enjambment occurs between two adverbs related to the same verb	another crab grabs him and pulls him back down
pb_adv_prep	Enjambment occurs between an adverb and the prepositional phrase modifying that adverb	crawling in and out of beds
pb_phrasal_verb	Enjambment occurs between a phrasal verb and the preposition/particle related to that phrasal verb	I won't blame him for getting out
pb_to_verb	Enjambment occurs between a 'to' preposition and the verb it introduces	We began our unholy alliance to test the literary waters
pb_comp	Enjambment occurs between elements that are part of a comparison structure	Better to be human Than God
pb_relword	Enjambment occurs between a conjunction and the proposition it introduces	You wrote me that letter and I answered
Expansion Type		
ex_subj_verb	Enjambment occurs between a subject and its governing verb	[...] all in uppercase, and you knew famous artists
ex_dobj_verb	Enjambment occurs between a direct object and its governing verb	her dressing did outbrave all the pride the fields then have

Tag	Description	Example
ex_dobj_pverb	Enjambment occurs between a phrasal verb and its direct object	haven't you heard of the thirties?
ex_verb_adjunct	Enjambment occurs between an adverbial clause and its governing verb	And then awakens in the morning to write

In case of ex_verb_adjunct, the type of adjunct should be specified (time, location, manner...):

1. Afterward I went past what you had passed
2. Before we met and you what I had passed.

01 02 [ex_verb_adjunct_time] [smooth] [retro]

Style annotation

Tag	Description	Example
abrupt	The meaning of the enjambed sentence flows over the next line but there is some sort of pause occurring somewhere before the end of that line as well	I am not prone to weeping, as our sex Commonly are; the want of which vain dew Perchance shall dry your pities; but I have [that honourable...]
smooth	The meaning of the enjambed sentence flows over the next line and no pause occurs before the end of that line	Hold fast to dreams For if dreams die Life is a broken-winged bird That cannot fly.

Meaning annotation

Tag	Description	Example
retro	The line or sentence is syntactically complete but the following line contains semantic information necessary to understand the sentence right	Life is a barren field Frozen with snow
pro	The line or sentence is syntactically incomplete and must be completed by the following line	Below me young lovers Tread the sweet ground

Example

1. A thing of beauty is a joy for ever:
2. Its loveliness increases; it will never
3. Pass into nothingness; but still will keep
4. A bower quiet for us, and a sleep
5. Full of sweet dreams, and health, and quiet breathing.

01 02 [] [] []

02 03 [pb_verb_adv] [abrupt] [pro]

03 04 [ex_dobj_verb] [abrupt] [pro]

04 05 [pb_noun_adj] [abrupt] [pro]